

Polarographic Behaviour and Kinetics of Electrode Reaction of Neodymium(III) in Potassium Chloride

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Manuscript received 18 July 1983, revised 12 June 1984, accepted 19 January 1985

Polarographic behaviour and kinetics of electrode reaction of Nd^{III} in potassium chloride in presence of 0.01% gelatin between pH 1.9 to 3.0 value have been investigated. It is observed that Nd^{III} gives an irreversible polarographic wave in 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm^{-3} potassium chloride, which attains a quasi-reversible nature on increasing the supporting electrolyte concentration and finally it becomes almost a reversible reduction wave in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} potassium chloride. The reduction wave is of diffusion controlled nature. A shift in the half-wave potential to more negative value is observed with decreasing pH of the test solutions. Reversible half-wave potentials have been calculated by Gelling's method. Kinetic parameters of quasi-reversible and irreversible waves have also been evaluated.

THE polarographic reduction of trivalent rare earth sulphate solutions have been studied without any supporting electrolyte¹, in which two successive waves were obtained each for +2 and metallic states, respectively. Lithium chloride and tetramethylammonium iodide as supporting electrolyte have also been used for the polarographic reduction of Nd^{III} , in which poor limiting current was observed². Misumi and Aihara have reported the electroreduction of Nd^{III} by cyclic-voltametric technique³. The use of varying concentration of supporting electrolyte on the polarographic reduction and kinetics of electrode reaction of various depolarisers have been reported by many workers⁴⁻⁸. Recently, the present authors have reported the reduction of Ce^{III} and Pr^{III} in varying concentrations of potassium chloride to study the kinetics of electrode reaction of the reduction process at the dropping-mercury electrode^{9,10}. A survey of existing literature reveals that the polarographic study of Nd^{III} in potassium chloride has not been reported. The present paper deals with the polarographic behaviour of Nd^{III} in varying concentrations of potassium chloride and kinetics of the reduction process at the DME surface.

Experimental

The chemicals used during the experiment were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Nd^{III} chloride solution was prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of the metal oxide in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid. It was subsequently evaporated to dryness, and finally the residue was extracted in conductivity water and standardised¹¹. The pH of the test solution was adjusted with hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions.

An automatic pen recording polarograph CIC (Baroda, India) was used to record the polarograms.

The characteristics of the dropping-mercury electrode in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} potassium chloride, open circuit were $m=2.37$ mg/s, $t=3.0$ s at 35 cm of effective height of the mercury column ($m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=2.136$ $\text{mg}^{2/3}\text{s}^{-1/6}$). Potentials were measured against saturated calomel electrode. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution to deaerate it. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to measure the pH of the test solution. All the measurements were made at room temperature ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The pH of the test solution played an important role in the polarographic reduction of Nd^{III} in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} potassium chloride containing 0.01% gelatin. Precipitation occurred at pH 5.2 and above. On lowering the pH to 3.5, a single reduction wave was observed with $E_{1/2} = -1.71$ V vs SCE but the shape of the wave was feeble. In the pH range from 3.5 to 1.9, a reproducible, well defined reduction wave was observed. The half-wave potential shifted to the negative direction with decreasing pH. Below pH 1.90 the reduction wave became distorted. In the absence of gelatin, polarographic maximum was observed, which was suppressed in presence 0.01% gelatin. The results are listed in Table 1.

Nd^{III} in varying concentration of potassium chloride (0.1 to 1.0 mol dm^{-3}) in the pH range between 1.90 to 3.0 showed a single well defined reduction wave. The limiting current was diffusion controlled in each case, which was confirmed by plotting i_d vs square root of effective mercury head, and i_d vs C (concentration of the depolariser). These plots were linear and passed through the origin. The value of diffusion current constant was found to be 4.22 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{A m mol}^{-1} \text{mg}^{-2/3} \text{s}^{-1/6}$. The

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON HALF WAVE POTENTIAL AND DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANTS OF 2 m mol dm⁻³ Nd^{III} IN 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KCl+0.01% GELATIN

pH	I	
	$\frac{-E_{1/2} \text{ vs SCE}}{V}$	$\frac{\mu A \text{ m mol}^{-1} \text{ l mg}^{-1/2} \text{ s}^{1/2}}$
<1.70	Distorted wave	
1.90	1.83	4.10
2.26	1.792	4.26
2.40	1.79	4.16
2.65	1.765	4.26
3.0	1.74	4.34
3.5	1.71	4.16
4.5	1.71	—
>5.0	Poor limiting current	

number of electrons involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of De Vries and Kroon¹², using DME as cathode and mercury pool as anode. In the present system the charge number of the reaction, *n*, was found to be 3. Knowing the value of *n* the diffusion coefficient was calculated by Ilkovic equation¹³ at different concentrations of the supporting electrolyte, and are listed in Table 2.

The plot of $\log [i/(i_a - i)]$ vs E_{de} ¹⁴ for each polarogram was similar but the reciprocal slope

value decreased from 55 to 20 mV on subsequent increase of potassium chloride concentration.

According to Goto and Tachi¹⁵, for a totally irreversible wave, if the value of α in relation

$$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = -\frac{0.0577 V}{\alpha n_a} \quad (1)$$

is less than 0.5, the electrode process is said to be of irreversible nature. In varying concentrations of potassium chloride from 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ the value of α is <0.5, above 0.6 mol dm⁻³ concentration the value is >0.5, and at 1.0 mol dm⁻³ and above the value is nearly unity and the wave is almost reversible which is confirmed by log plot slope value. According to Meites¹⁴ the value of α may, in principle, vary from nearly 0 to 1, and in most cases it is not far from 0.5.

Koutecky's method¹⁶ as extended by Meites and Israel¹⁷ was used to calculate the kinetic parameters, by using the following equations for irreversible polarographic waves obtained in 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 1, A, B, C).

$$E_{de} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1}{i_a - i} \quad (2)$$

$$E_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{t,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_0^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE CONCENTRATION ON 2 m mol dm⁻³ Nd^{III} + 0.01% GELATIN AT pH 2.4 ± 0.02

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	$-E_{1/2} \text{ vs SCE}$		D × 10 ⁶ cm ² /s	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ mV	α	$K_{s,h}$ × 10 ⁴ cm/s	$K_{f,h}$ cm/s
	V	V					
0.1	1.77	—	8.58	53	0.35	—	1.149 × 10 ⁻³⁰
0.2	1.772	—	8.36	48	0.41	—	2.643 × 10 ⁻²²
0.5	1.78	—	8.14	38	0.51	—	2.585 × 10 ⁻⁴³
0.6	1.782	1.772	8.14	32	0.58	3.8	—
0.8	1.785	1.778	7.70	27	0.70	8.2	—
0.9	1.788	1.780	7.41	23	0.82	9.6	—
1.0	1.79	1.79	7.28	20	—	—	—

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 2 mM Nd^{III} (in presence of 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 in varying concentration of potassium chloride: (A) 0.1, (B) 0.2, (C) 0.5, (D) 0.6, (E) 0.8, and (F) 1.0 M.

where $K_{f,h}^0$ = forward rate constant at 0 V vs NHE, and α = transfer coefficient.

Gellings' method¹⁸ was used to evaluate the kinetic parameters of quasi-reversible waves, obtained in 0.6 to 0.9 mol dm⁻³ potassium chloride concentrations (Fig. 1, D, E, F). The reversible half-wave potentials were calculated, which involves the plot of

$$E + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{i}{i_d - i} \text{ vs } i \quad (4)$$

and extrapolate it to zero value. The standard rate constant $K_{s,h}$ and transfer coefficient α have also been calculated. In the present system the value of $K_{s,h}$ was found to be of the order of 10⁻⁴ cm/s, which confirms that the electrode process is quasi-reversible in 0.6 to 0.9 mol dm⁻³ potassium chloride concentration. All the polarographic data have been listed in Table 2.

All these criteria indicate to a conclusion that for Nd^{III}, an irreversible polarographic wave is obtained in 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ potassium chloride concentration which attains a quasi-reversible nature on increasing the supporting electrolyte concentration and finally it becomes a well defined almost reversible three-electron reduction wave in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ potassium chloride concentration and above, as also observed by Verma *et al.*⁵ in the reduction of Ni^{II} in potassium thiocyanate.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.K.C.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi and Government of Madhya Pradesh for the award of Teacher Fellowship.

Thanks are also due to Prof. A. V. Mahajani, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar for providing facilities.

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